

Digital Technology Skills Needed for Teaching and Learning of Office Technology and Management Education Courses in Colleges of Education Delta State

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Abstract

Digital literacy skills has become very important in the preparation of Office Technology and Management Education teachers, going by the fact that there is dearth of O.T.M.E Teachers with adequate skills in digital literacy. One research question and hypothesis guided the study. Descriptive survey design was adopted. The entire population of 54 lecturers randomly selected from Colleges of Education in Delta State offering Office Technology and Management Education courses was use 4- point type Likert scale with 20 items adopted. Data collected were analysed using mean and standard deviation and null hypothesis was tested using the independent t-test at 0.05 level of significant. The findings revealed that lecturers required digital literacy skills for teaching and learning of office technology and management education courses in Colleges of education. Also, there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of highly experienced and less experienced lecturers on the digital literacy skills required for teaching and learning O.T.M.E courses ($t_{(52)}=0.764, p>0.05$). The study concluded that the design of effective learning environments and embedding digital literacy are critical. It was therefore recommended among others that the authorities of colleges of Education should ensure adequate implementation of policies that will propel the adoption, development and deployment of digital literacy for teaching and learning in the areas of improved digital equipment and machines.

Keywords: Digital Literacy Skills, Teaching and Learning, Office Technology and Management

Introduction

The digital world is rapidly penetrating the education and skills domain, with technology gradually being used to deliver education, knowledge and skills in new and innovative ways. This penetration is coupled with future changes to the mode and pattern of work, which are themselves affected by the current climate of economic uncertainty, as well as by political shifts. Office Technology and Management Education is a field of study concerned with how to teach business and vocational subjects and skills to students at various grade level. Mansueto Ventures (2021), Office Technology and Management Education is a term that encompasses a number of methods used to teach students the fundamentals of business practices. Office Technology and Management provides undergraduates with the knowledge, skills and techniques to start up and manage small businesses effectively Mansue to Ventures. Office technology and management offers various skills training in business studies, commerce, accounting, word processing, computer entrepreneurship education, office practice, marketing, business management among others at various grade levels (Ejeka, 2017). One of the major objectives of Office technology and management is to provide technical competencies to undergraduates to have a successful career as professional. Similarly, Edokpolar (2017) noted that the actual goals of business education shall be to: Prepare students for specific career in office occupations, Equip students with the required skills for job creation and entrepreneurship; and Expose students with knowledge about business, including a good blend of computer technology, with incorporates Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Digital Technology includes the use of personal computers, digital television, radio, mobile phones, robot. The term is used to describe the use of digital resources to effectively find, analyse, create, communication and use information in a digital contexts (Edokpolar 2017). This includes the use of web tools, digital media tools, programming tools and software applications. Bates (2011) observes that digital technology includes all types of electronic equipment and applications that use information in the form of Numeric Code. This information is usually in binary code that is, code that can be represented by two strings of only two numeric characters (Os and Is). Devices that process and use digital information include Personal computers, calculators, automobiles, traffic lights controllers, compact disc players, cellular telephones, communications satellites and high-definition television sets.

Digital Technology skill on the other hand involves the ability, confidence critical and responsible use of digital tools, and engagement with digital technologies for learning, at work and participation in society. It includes information and data literacy, communication and collaboration, digital content creation (including programming), safety (including digital well-being and competencies related to cyber security and problem solving (UNESCO, 2020). This definition emphasizes engagement with digital literacy's, the growing importance of digital technology use for education purposes and the need to actively promote digital technology in teaching and learning and seize technological opportunities so that education can keep on with other sectors. Similarly, Heinz (2016) views digital competence as the confident, critical and creative use of digital technologies to achieve goals related to work, employability, learning, leisure, inclusion and/participation in society. According to Ottestad (2014) digital skill is defined as the teacher's ability to use ICT with as good pedagogical-didactic ICT understanding and to be aware of how this might impact the learning strategies and educational formation of pupils. This means that the teacher must make decisions about what kind of digital tools should be used in teaching situation, how they should be and why. In order to attain these skills, individual needs to acquire basic training. Skill is a vital aspect of business education training. It is the ability to perform a task with the minimum considerable time, energy, or both.

According to Green (2015), skill is a personal quality with three key features, namely: Productive (using skill is productive of value), expandable (skills are enhanced by training and development) and social (skills are socially determined). What characterised skill as captured by Proctor and Dutta in Nakayama and Sutcliffe (2017) include: A skill is not innate but must be learned, a skill behaviour is goal directed, a skill develops in response to some demand imposed by the task environment, a skill is acquired when the behaviour is highly integrated and well organised. Through experience, the components of the behaviour become structure into coherent patterns, and cognitive demands are reduced as skill is acquired. Generally, skills are classified into hard and soft skills. Hard skills are also referred to as technical skills; such skills focus more on practical abilities. Kagan and Kindness (2021) defined hard skills as learned abilities acquired and enhanced through practice, repetition and education. For Doyle (2019) hard skills are teachable abilities or skills sets that are easy to quantify and learned in classroom, through books or other training

materials, or on the job. They can also be required through training programs, apprenticeships, short-term training classes, online courses and certification programs.

Teachable in this context means that hard skill can be developed through dedicated training over a period of time. According to Cheary (2020) hard skills are specific abilities. It means that such skills cannot be transferred from one industry to another. Teaching and Learning in an act whereby the teacher imparts or transfers knowledge, behaviour, skills, values or preferences to a learner and the learner acquires or modifies what is taught and learnt to a potential change in synthesizing information, depth of the knowledge, attitudes or behaviour relative to the type and range of experience. (Akpomi, 2018). It is a system involving the teacher, the learner and the learning task as well as the learning environment. Teaching therefore is a set of events, outside and within the learning environment which are design to support internal process of learning, while learning is about a change: the change brought about developing new skills, understanding scientific law and changing attitude. Office Technology and Management Education involves teaching students that fundamentals, theories and processes of business education, at this stage occurs at several levels including secondary education and higher education, with the greatest activity occurring in the latter. Office technology and management typically prepares students for an occupation in business or a business related field or a teaching career in academics (Shivangi 2020)

This business education helps individuals to acquire saleable skills that will enable them fit into various business organisations or be self-employed in the absence of paid employment. Business education as discipline is expected to expose its recipients to diversity of curricula, hence, it is that type of education that inculcate in its recipient attitude, knowledge, skills, values that is required in the business world (Okeke & Opeyemi 2018). A well-articulated business education, if properly implemented with efficiently delivered infrastructure can help bridge the skill p\gaps existing between the school graduates and the requirements of the corporate business organisation thereby reducing the huge cost of human resource development in business organisation. Digitalisation has created a glaring need for Business education lecturers to acquire relevant skills in order to bring up the calibre of graduate that will fit squarely onto the digital work trends. It is globally recognized that the use of digital technologies in teaching and learning is a relevant and functional way of

providing education to learners that will assist in imbuing in them the required capacity for the world of work.

Additionally, effective application of digital technologies in teaching will facilitate the realization of stated objective of any educational programmes through improve innovativeness, curiosity and creativity of the learners. Shivangi 2020. Ezugwu (2018) noted that most lecturers and students of business education have not been making effective use of digital resources in their academic work.

The hindrances and constraints come as a result of manpower shortage wastage, shortage of technological facilities and lack of knowledge and use of computer aided instruction. Added to this, is the fact the fact that most digital facilities are not available in the college of education and where they exist, they are either not functional or inadequate and lecturers and students do not employ digital technology for teaching or learning. Umoru (2018) reports that in Nigeria, many business education teachers lack skills in technology application as a result of which they face their work with fear and trepidation. This has continually hampered teaching and learning. Furthermore, the students of this generation are very familiar with new technology, especially social media platforms. This situation compounds teacher's problem as they are challenged. They often become isolated and confused. It is against this backdrop that the study examines digital technology literacy required for teaching and learning of office technology and management courses in Colleges of Education in Delta State

Statement of the Problem

Effective teaching in any learning environment requires demonstration of various skills which invariably enable students to learn by improving their knowledge, skills, attitudes and values. The office technology and management education lecturers are vital in the impartation of required skills to the students through the acquisition and possession of the required digital technology skills.

However, Okoli and Wagbara (2016), observed that despite the enthusiasm towards the use of digital technologies seem to have little impact in the classroom because some office technology education lecturers are showing signs of apathy towards digital technologies. Similarly, Okoli and Wagbara (2016) observed that many of the teachers lack knowledge and skills to use digital technologies and in addition are not enthusiastic about the changes due to inadequate training to

meet up with technological flux. There is also the fear of the unknown which lead to resistant behaviour. Nwosu and Mbaezue (2016) confirm that there is dearth of office technology and management education teachers with adequate skills in digital technologies, with the result that non-specialists are often called upon to teach O.T.M.E courses. The inability of the teachers to use computers and other modern technology to teach Office Technology and Management Education has hampered the teaching of the subject. Unfortunately, this has not been clearly laid bare by the previous research efforts. Therefore, the problem of this study is to identify the required digital skills for teaching and learning office technology and management courses in colleges of education in Delta state. This is in view of the inadequate knowledge of some lecturers in teaching using digital technological tools. The purpose of this study is to identify the digital literacy skills required for teaching and learning Office Technology and Management Education courses in College of Education, Delta State.

Research Questions

To what extent are digital literacy skills required for teaching and learning office technology and management education courses in colleges of education in Delta State.

Research Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of highly experienced and less experience respondents on the digital literacy skills required for teaching and learning office technology and management education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Methodology

The descriptive survey design was used for the conduct of the study. The population of the study consisted of all lecturers in school of Office Technology and Management in three colleges of Education in Delta State. These institutions include, Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba, Delta State, College of Education Warri, Delta State, Delta State of Education Mosogar.

The entire study population of 54 was used for the study since the population was not too large. There was therefore no sampling. The instrument used was the Digital Technology Skills Required for Teaching and Learning Office Technology and Management Courses Questionnaire

(DTSRTLBEQ). The questionnaire consisted of 20 item based on the purpose of the study and the research question. The instrument was validated by two chief lecturers in the School of Business Education, Federal College of Education (Tech). Asaba Delta State. A pilot study was conducted at the College of Education Warri, Delta State. Cronbach Alpha reliability method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.73. each of the items was assigned four response options of High Extent (HE-4Points), Moderate Extent (ME-3Points), Low Extent (LE-2Points) and No Extent (NE-1Points). A total of 54 questionnaires were filled and returned consisting of 37 (68.52%) highly experienced lecturers (1-9years of service). The data collected were analysed using the mean and standard deviation. The mean was used to answer the research while the standard deviation was used to determine the closeness or otherwise of the responses from the mean. Positive decision rule for this study was established at a mean of 2.50 and above while any mean less than that was regarded as negative. The null hypothesis stated was tested using the t-test at 0.05 level of the significance. Hypothesis of no significant difference was accepted when the observed probability value was greater than or equal to 0.05 level of significance where the calculated probability value was less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 1: Mean and Standard deviation of response on the extent to which digital technology skills are required for teaching and learning business education courses

S/N	Item Statement	X	SD	Remark
1	Ability to use different internet connection options to connect to the web	3.89	0.37	High extent
2	Ability to use interactive multimedia digital technologies for teaching and learning	3.65	0.70	High extent
3	Ability to use the electronic mail (e-mail) or list server to mail teaching contents.	3.87	0.48	High extent
4	Ability to use the search engine such as yahoo, google, MSM to access teaching and learning contents	3.63	0.78	High extent
5	Ability to use digital survey tools (Surveymonkey, Zoomerang, among others for online survey and research	3.20	0.83	Moderate extent
6	Ability to upload and download teaching and learning contents through file transfer service	3.79	0.41	High extent

7	Ability to use digital students response system for instant feedback during teaching and learning	3.24	0.41	High extent
8	Ability to use interactive e-books for educational purposes	3.26	0.73	Moderate Extent
9	Ability to use Web applications such as web 2.0 tools for interactive teaching and learning	3.72	0.56	High extent
10	Ability to use cloud computing for storing and sharing files	3.63	0.71	High extent
11	Ability to select and guide students on selecting mobile educational apps for teaching and learning	3.91	0.35	High extent
12	Ability to use social networking services to post teaching contents	3.43	0.77	Moderate extent
13	Ability to use the wireless fidelity (WI-FI) to gain teaching contents	3.79	0.53	High extent
14	Ability to use collaborative services to post teaching contents	3.31	0.64	Moderate extent
15	Ability to organize online conference and discussion groups with students on the web.	3.59	0.77	High extent
16	Ability to use accessibility features of mobile devices Such as voiceover, speak selection, zoom etc to view and listen to teaching contents	3.48	0.61	Moderate extent
17	Knowledge of file systems, data security and cryptography In databases	3.80	0.56	High extent
18	Ability to create hypertext and hypermedia pages for education use	3.06	0.86	Moderate Extent
19	Ability to use web database programming using PHP	3.26	0.78	Moderate Extent
20	Ability to use web components such as plug-ins	3.02	0.96	Moderate Extent
	Decision mean	3.53	0.66	High extent

Table 1 above shows that the responses of lecturers on the digital technology skills required for teaching and learning business courses in tertiary institutions. The result revealed that all the digital technology skills items outlined were required to high extent for teaching and learning of business education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State with a weighted average mean of 3.53.

Items 5,7,8,12,14,16,18,19 and 20 were however required a moderate extent with mean scores between 3.02 to 3.48. All the 20 responses of the respondents are not wide spread, they are close to the mean. This implies that digital technology skills are required to high extent for teaching and learning of business education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Test of Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of high experienced and less experienced respondents on the digital literacy skills required for teaching and learning Office Technology and Management Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State

Table 2: Summary of t-test of the difference between the mean responses highly experienced and less experienced lecturers on the digital technology skills required for teaching and learning business education courses

Group	N	Mean	SD	t-cal	Df	p-value	Decision
Highly experienced	37	3.65	0.47				
Less experienced	17	3.58	0.20	0.764	52	0.447	NS

$p > 0.05$

The data in Table 2 reveals that there are 37 highly experienced lecturers and 17 less experienced lecturers. The response of highly experienced and less experienced lecturers indicated that digital technology skills are required to a high extent for teaching and learning business education courses in tertiary institutions ($X=3.65$; $SD=0.47$) and ($X = 3.58$; $SD = 0.20$). Their responses are close to the mean as the standard deviations are very low. The table reveals that there was no significant difference between the mean rating of highly experienced and less experienced lecturers on the digital technology skills required for teaching and learning business education courses in tertiary institutions ($t\text{-cal}=.E1) =0.764$, $P>0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of highly experienced and less experienced respondents on the digital technology skills required for teaching and learning business education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State was not rejected. This implies that highly experienced and less experienced lecturers did not differ in their responses regarding the digital technology skills required for teaching and learning business education courses in tertiary institutions.

Discussion Findings

The study sought to determine the extent to which technology skills are required for teaching and learning business education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The null hypothesis stated that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of highly experienced and less experienced respondents on the digital technology skills required for teaching and learning business education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The result showed that ability to use different internet connections options; interactive multimedia digital technologies, electronic mail (email) or list server, search engines and file transfer services were required to a high extent. Other digital skills required to a high extent are ability to use web applications, cloud computing, mobile educational apps, wireless fidelity (WI-FI), ability to organize online conferences and knowledge of life systems and data security. Also the finding revealed that the ability to use digital survey tools, digital student response systems, interactive e-books, social networking services, collaborative services, accessibility features of mobile devices, ability to create hypertext and hypermedia pages, ability to use web database programming and ability to use web components were required to a moderate extent for teaching and learning business education courses in tertiary institutions. The findings further revealed that there was no significant different between the mean ratings on highly experienced and less experienced lecturers on the digital technology skills required for teaching and learning business education courses in tertiary institutions ($t_{52} = 0.764$, $P > 0.05$). This finding corroborates that of Zakka, Bewaran and Moris (2021) who maintain that the knowledge and skills which business education lecturers require at present must reflect the growing use of digital technologies. This will aid in imparting the needed skills in students who can function effectively in a knowledge-driven economy. Heinz (2016) expresses a similar view and maintains that digital competence involves the confident, critical and creative use of digital technologies to achieve goals related to work, employability, learning, leisure, inclusion and/or participation in society. This means that the teacher must take decisions about what kind of digital tools should be used in each teaching situations, how they should be used and why.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that the design of effective learning environments and embedding digital technologies and critical. This can serve as catalysts for

teachers to experiment new things, explore creative alternatives and reflect on their own practices. Office Technology and Management Education programme that equips an individual with functional and suitable skills, knowledge, attitude and value that would enable him/her operates in the environment he/she finds himself/herself.

Recommendations

The implantation of polices that will propel the adoption, development and deployment of digital technologies for teaching and learning is crucial. This can be achieved through regular review of the curriculum, improved funding for the provision of adequate teaching and learning equipment and the necessary infrastructure for teaching using digital technologies. There is need for the systematic re-training of teachers to cope with the trend of digital technologies. Individual teachers should also make efforts towards self-analysis for personal skill development in the use of digital technologies. This can be done through job related re-skilling and up-skilling programmes, so as to help teachers acquire the necessary digital technology skills.

Managements and heads of departments should ensure that technicians are always at hand to assist students and teachers who may encounter technical difficulties that may hinder and slow-down the teaching and learning process. Similarly, technologies will help teachers with some difficult applications where necessary, as it may not be possible for an individual lecturer to be an expert in all aspects of digital technology applications.

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